

The Influence Project Planning on the Performance of Church Funded Projects in Tanzania: A Case Study of Cardinal Rugambwa Hospital and St Francis Training College

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Abstract: *The study is about the; the influence project planning on the performance of church funded projects in Tanzania: A Case Study of Cardinal Rugambwa Hospital and St Francis Training College. A descriptive survey design was used to collect primary data from random sample of 350 respondents (project managers and the community). The study found that project planning positively and significantly affects the performance of Church-funded projects. The study recommends that more people with technical skills are needed, especially in information systems for monitoring and assessment. Church funded projects should ensure that there is adequate early planning for project monitoring and evaluation activities, including human resources and stakeholder involvement in the development and implementation of the monitoring and evaluation system.*

Keywords: Project Planning, Project Performance, Church Funded Projects, Tanzania.

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1. Introduction

Church-funded projects are projects with a focus on social and environmental goals, and whose surpluses are primarily reinvested for those purposes in projects or in the community rather than to give returns to owners and shareholders as profit (Leadbeater, 2013). The modern global trend of corporate social responsibility, or CSR, is growing as academics and businesspeople recognize how critical it is to address social and environmental needs of society and close the wealth-poverty gap. One example of this is church-funded projects.

A church-funded project in the United States focuses on meeting the unmet needs of society and the environment, providing a completely new socially conscious business vision (Leadbeater, 2013). Church-funded projects take on various tasks such as building parks, schools, health centers, planting trees, and other social needs. These projects improve an individual's or institution's reputation, gain them special respect from their peers, lessen pollution, and generate employment opportunities. People, organizations, and corporate entities involved in projects funded by churches take into account the dimensions of social response and social contribution. Some choose to use cost-benefit analysis to go above and beyond the legal requirements, while others volunteer out of a strong sense of duty to help the community regardless of the costs or benefits. It has been challenging for these organizations to compete, with the exception of a few nations, due to a lack of legislative protection and government backing (Pattiniemi, 2010).

Missionaries in Europe have played a significant role in mitigating the socioeconomic hardships faced by individuals across various

regions of the globe, primarily through projects funded by churches. This has been mainly achieved by giving people access to spiritual hydration as well as food, healthcare, and education (Flannery, 2009). Occasionally, these programs come to an abrupt end because a particular minister leaves the organization, donors pass away, or the organizations that fund them stop providing funding.

The abrupt halt of church-supported programs in South Africa has left numerous projects incomplete, dashed hopes, and unmet promises for those who relied on them for their basic needs and to improve their status in terms of food, education, and healthcare. In many instances, this has led to challenges in overseeing these projects, their eventual closure, or, at the very least, a decrease in the number of people benefiting from them. During these periods, various stakeholders and recipients of these projects face challenges with the church-funded efforts and express regret over the absence of sustainable frameworks that could have aided in navigating these unforeseen yet significant and challenging situations. This underscores the importance of ensuring the sustainability of church-supported projects within the church as a proactive measure to ensure their successful completion and, in the end, the fulfillment of the original intentions of those who initiated them (Pattiniemi, 2010).

In Uganda, the financial capacity of a church organization is comprised of resources that allow it to manage its basic commercial activities while simultaneously seizing opportunities and addressing unanticipated risks. The fact that churches operate in places where there is a strong need for services that must constantly be provided exacerbates the problem. For non-profit organizations, financial sustainability means preserving or

expanding internal services while bolstering resilience against intermittent, transient economic shocks (Bowman, 2011).

There are more than 5000 NGOs operating in Tanzania, according to a 2004 report by Kaguta. The same report also showed that the effectiveness of these organizations' projects is generally poor, with 35 percent of their initiatives failing at an early stage. This is due to the fact that grouping success factors and elucidating their interactions are prioritized over identifying the specific factors that impact the project's success. A few of the challenges Tanzanian church-funded projects face include the need to maintain financial sustainability while pursuing the church's mission. To get past these obstacles, these organizations must be guided by a sustainable strategy. According to Masoka and Zimmerman (2010), nonprofits including those supported by churches cannot be judged on the effectiveness of their high-impact programs in the absence of a successful financial sustainability strategy.

The Church has played a pivotal role in initiating community-oriented projects in Tanzania. Its objective is to empower local groups and institutions by granting them direct authority over investment choices, project design, execution, and oversight. This is achieved through a framework that emphasizes inclusive participation, effective church governance, and the implementation of projects (Karanja, 2014). The management of diversity, the strategies used to bring together varied communities, and the approach to addressing the interests and differences of members can significantly influence the success of these initiatives.

According to Thomas, Delisle, Jugdev, and Buckle (2011), inadequate project management accounts for thirty percent of all project failures. According to Thomas, Delisle, Jugdev, and Buckle (2011), there is a correlation between the project identification process and its performance. They discovered that because of inadequate management of the initial identification process, 30% of all projects are canceled midstream, and more than 50% of completed projects wind up being up to 190 percent over budget and 220 percent behind schedule. Projects can leverage the knowledge base of stakeholders when two key issues are addressed correctly: stakeholder analysis and involvement in the identification process (Mitropoulos and Howell 2012).

Furthermore, since integrated project teams would improve project outcomes, they must be formed (Lahdenperä, 2012; Cohen, 2010). The process of problem analysis, risk management analysis, and selecting the right objectives are the other three primary areas of interest in project management. Projects are meant to solve problems. Time, energy, and resources will be wasted if the incorrect project is selected.

Globally, many projects are still falling short of their targets. With little to show for the money spent on these initiatives, many of the funds were lost. The poor performance of these Church Relief Services projects seriously impairs the operations of both NGO programs. After evaluating a range of projects and activities, teams from international non-governmental organizations (NGOs) such as UNIDO have found a lack of high-quality documentary evidence. Even though numerous relief services were supplied to the various projects, their overall impact was insignificant. Numerous studies have examined some of the factors that affect an NGO's performance. Monitoring systems, project planning process, poor communication, and poor project risk management are all contributing factors to Church project underperformance,

according to Ondieki and Matonda (2013). Fewer studies, though, have looked at the effect of project planning on performance of church funded projects in Tanzania.

2. Literature Review

Project performance, which can be measured using a range of factors (including project relevance, impact, and sustainability), refers to how well a project fulfilled the objectives of the various stakeholders in its finished form (Leadbeater, 2013). One metric used to determine whether a project is successful or unsuccessful is project performance. It includes a number of things, like completing tasks on time, on budget, following project schedules, and producing high-quality outcomes that either meet or surpass expectations (Project Management Institute, 2022). Basically, a component of project performance is anything that affects a project's final output, whether directly or indirectly. Thus, in the context of the present study, project performance refers to the process of gauging the advancement and success of a project. It assesses a project's management effectiveness, execution efficiency, and potential for success.

The Resource-Based Theory (RBT), initially introduced by Penrose in 2009, stands as the leading contemporary theory of business strategy (Kay, 2005). This theory is centered on the concept of economic rent and views a company as a bundle of capabilities. It is distinguished by its coherence and ability to integrate various aspects of strategic decision-making, making it superior to alternative strategies (Kay, 2005). The Resource-Based View offers critical insights into the success of businesses possessing valuable, rare, unique, and well-managed resources (Barney, 1995). Its widespread acceptance in scholarly publications and inclusion in key strategic texts underscores its popularity among both academics and practitioners across undergraduate, master's, and executive levels.

Building on the RBV, Hoopes, Madsen, and Walker (2003) delve deeper into the factors that distinguish firms and propose a comprehensive theory of competitive diversity. The RBV's explanatory power is somewhat limited, as it often assumes rather than hypothesizes the causes of differences in firm performance, which can be attributed to variations in resources and capabilities. The theory's lack of clarity and specific boundaries make it challenging to fully grasp its potential contributions. The Resource-Based View's ambiguity, particularly in defining its core premise and establishing clear boundaries, hinders productive discussions. Additionally, the theory's focus on internal firm characteristics to explain strategy and performance overlooks other potential sources of competitive diversity, such as non-sticky resources (or capabilities) and the role they play in the competitive landscape. Competitive diversity refers to the consistent and enduring differences in performance among competitors.

The Resource-Based View explains firm diversity in strategy and performance by highlighting internal firm characteristics. This theory identifies resources and capabilities as key sources of competitive advantage, as they are part of the organized, unique set of factors that define a firm. Resources encompass a company's accumulated assets, including everything it can utilize for product development, production, and marketing. They are protected by legal rights, allowing businesses to exercise ownership over them (Amit and Shoemaker, 1993), enabling firms to operate

autonomously from other parts of the business (Camisón, 2005), and serving as inputs in the production process to transform inputs into outputs that meet consumer needs (Grant, 1991). RBV theory identifies resources and capabilities as two related sources of advantages because they are part of the organized, distinctive set of factors that make up a firm. A company's resources are all of its accumulated assets, including everything it can use to develop, produce, and/or market its products. Resources have the potential for legal protection, allowing businesses to exercise property rights over them. The availability of resources does not entirely guarantee the success of the project. There are several other factors both internal and external that when combined together may bring about maximum performance of the project. These factors may include project planning, location of the project and external factors such as auditing systems.

The stakeholder theory suggests that in community projects, it's crucial to involve community members' right from the start. It also argues that all individuals or groups participating in an organization's efforts benefit, and that the significance of each stakeholder's interests isn't always clear (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). As community members become more active, there's an enhancement in social unity as they start to appreciate working together with others and groups. Moreover, it contributes to the economy by promoting donations for community improvement and by supporting the growth of skills, which in turn enhances job opportunities and increases community wealth, while also providing residents with the necessary connections and skills to prevent social exclusion. However, the theory has its limitations, as it overlooks other important factors needed for project success. This is where resource-based theory steps in, as it offers crucial insights into why businesses with valuable, rare, unique, and well-managed resources tend to excel (Barney, 1995). Therefore, applying these two theories to the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the variables involved.

Magano (2008) points out that funding is a key element that can contribute to the success of a project. He also emphasizes the importance of considering the project's financial requirements in both its planning and sustainability proposals. According to Mihelcic and his team, Sustainable development, as defined in 2003, involves designing systems for industry and society that do not deplete natural resources or disrupt the balance of ecosystems, thereby maintaining or enhancing the quality of life for people without compromising future economic prospects or harming the environment, society, or human health. The success of a project can be greatly influenced by its planning and execution. For example, development officers can play a role in ensuring the lasting impact of their interventions on vulnerable communities by promoting community involvement, being flexible in the face of challenges, and enhancing the ability of community members to plan and manage future initiatives. The case studies reviewed highlighted these principles of project sustainability.

Development projects can take place in various settings. McDade (2004) suggests that the best approach is to first understand the needs of the community, including both men and women, before concentrating on projects that aim to improve and sustain their way of life. However, many projects are more narrowly focused, often due to the expertise of the organization implementing them.

The time frame for projects and the availability of funding are often constrained. Yet, the goal is for the impact of these projects and assistance to be enduring. Overcoming the challenge of sustaining projects over the long term is a significant obstacle in international development. Bishop (2001) notes that many projects have failed to achieve their goals due to various reasons. The approach to project planning and execution is critical. Each phase of the project should consider sustainability for success, especially when external support ends, as is common in international development efforts.

The UN (2002) identifies economic, social, and environmental sustainability as the foundational elements. Within the social pillar, McConville and Mihelcic (2007) break it down into three sub-elements: political unity, community involvement, and respect for cultural diversity. This led to the identification of five key factors essential for achieving sustainability in development. Kelly and Becker (2000) outline that through a comprehensive planning process, community involvement, and education, communities can identify local issues related to social, economic, and environmental aspects, and work towards ensuring the community's long-term well-being and sustainability.

3. Research Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design, concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular person or group (Kothari 2009). The study area was Ilala District located in Dar es Salaam. In this district two Church sponsored projects were chosen (Cardinal Rugambwa hospital located at Ukonga ward and St. Francis training college in Dar es Salaam located ward Pugu ward). These study areas were chosen because they are Church sponsored projects rendering public services to the community.

Simple random sampling technique was applied to select respondents who included the management team, facilitators and community members. Piloting was ensured that the questionnaire is free from ambiguity and the data generated is meaningfully analyzed in relation to the stated research questions, the same questionnaire was applied to all groups of respondents. This was done by administering (10% of the sample size) which is 40 participants which contained similar characteristics as the study area. After piloting, adjustments were made accordingly to address areas of concern. The data was subjected to correlation coefficient and a correlation of above 0.7 was obtained to prove the instruments reliability. Data were analyzed through descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages. The validity of theories was examined through the application of multiple regression analysis to determine the extent and importance of connections between the independent variable, project management, and the dependent variable, project performance of projects funded by churches. The general multiple regression equation for the project performance model was expressed in equation 1

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_n + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where Y depicts dependent variable

X_{1-4} are explanatory variables

ϵ is error term

β_{0-n} are parameter estimates

Replacing Y and X variables in equation 1, the structural model for this study's analysis will therefore be represented by equation 2.

$$PP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SP_1 + \beta_2 RP_2 + \beta_3 CP_3 + \beta_4 QC_3 + \epsilon \quad \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where

PP=Project performance

SP =Scope Planmning

CP=Cost Planning

QC=Quality Control

ϵ is essor term

β_{0-n} are parameter estimates

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Demographic Information

Respondents were also asked how long they had been working with Church funded projects. Their answers are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4. 1: Period Respondent has been working with Church funded projects

Years spent at the project	Frequency	Percentages
Less than 3 years	28	8.3
3 to 9 years	104	29.0
9 to 12 years	95	27.1
Above 12 years	28	8.3
None (community members)	95	27.1
Total	350	100.0
Qualification	Frequency	Percent (%)
Certificate	28	8.5
Diploma	49	13.4
Degree	217	59.8
Masters	35	11.0
PhD	21	7.3
Total	350	100.0

The findings indicate that 46.3% of participants had been involved in Church projects for a duration ranging from three to nine years, 39% had been engaged with Church groups for a period of nine to 12 years, and a combined total of 14.6% had been part of Church-backed initiatives for more than 12 years but less than three years. This suggests that the majority have had sufficient experience with Church-funded projects to grasp the topic being researched and to offer dependable and precise details about it.

Respondents were asked to indicate their highest level of education. Their answers are shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4. 2: Respondents Academic Qualification

Qualification	Frequency	Percent (%)
Certificate	28	8.5
Diploma	49	13.4
Degree	217	59.8
Masters	35	11.0
PhD	21	7.3
Total	350	100.0

The findings indicate that 59.8% of the participants possessed a college degree, with a smaller group, 13.4%, holding diplomas. Additionally, the survey included 11% with master's degrees, 8.5% with diplomas, and 7.3% with PhDs. This group of respondents is knowledgeable about the topic being researched and can offer trustworthy insights. Furthermore, it demonstrates that the majority of participants had the necessary qualifications to manage projects funded by the Church.

4.2 Influence of Project Planning on project performance

Participants were requested to share their views on the impact of project planning on the success of Church service initiatives. A four-point Likert scale was employed to evaluate the degree to which project planning impacted the outcomes of Church-funded projects. The categories were: minimal impact, moderate impact, significant impact, and profound impact, each assigned a score value of 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively. The combined answers are presented in Table 4.13, utilizing both frequency and percentage data.

Table 4.3: Extent at which Project Planning Influence Performance of Church funded projects

Items	Project Planning Influence	Frequency	Mean	Std. Dev.	Percent
Project scope planning	Low extent	28	4.146	.931	8.5
Resource planning	Moderate extent	84	3.842	.793	23.2
Cost planning and budgeting	Great extent	154	3.415	.543	43.9
Quality control	Very great extent	84	2.463	.592	24.4

Based on the findings, participants reported that the planning of projects significantly impacted the success of those funded by churches, to a great extent, an extremely great extent, a moderate extent, and to a minor extent, it had a slight impact on their performance. This indicates that the planning of projects plays a crucial role in determining the success of those funded by churches. Furthermore, the researcher was interested in understanding how various elements of project planning influenced the success of these church-funded projects.

Based on the findings, participants rated project scope planning high. The high score for project scope planning was attributed to its role in ensuring projects were completed on schedule, within budget, and satisfied the needs and expectations of stakeholders. It provided a structure for outlining the project's boundaries, dividing it into smaller, more manageable segments, and confirming its alignment with stakeholders and resource planning significantly influenced the success of Church-funded projects, particularly in organizing resources. Organizing resources, including human, financial, and other assets necessary for the project's effective execution, was deemed essential by participants, leading them to view it as crucial in the project's execution in the selected study areas.

Moreover, participants noted that costing and budgeting moderately impacted project performance, though it presented some challenges in adhering to the project's actual costs. A budget surplus or deficit of up to 10% was deemed acceptable for the project's success. However, participants highlighted that quality planning, had minimal effect on project performance. This was because quality planning relied heavily on the availability of other resources, such as project scope planning, budgeting, and cost. With these other factors in place, quality planning was considered easier to implement, leading participants to view it as less of a critical factor in project success.

4.3. Performance of Church funded projects

The study also asked respondents to indicate trends in various performance aspects of Church-funded projects over the past five years. Their answers are shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4. 4: Trend of Performance of Church funded projects Aspects

Performance of Church funded projects	Mean	Std. Dev.
Project completed within schedule.	2.539	.589
Project completed within cost	3.646	.636
Desired Quality & Safety	4.159	.808
Customer satisfaction	3.939	.866
Budgetary completion	4.220	.770

Based on the findings, participants reported that achieving budget goals had the highest score, followed by the adaptability of logistics operations. The importance of quality and safety, and the level of customer happiness were averagely rated. Additionally, the cost associated with finished projects has seen an improvement over the last five years was average. Nonetheless, participants noted that the ability to deliver projects on time has remained steady over the same period slightly poor performance.

Table 4.5 Regression Analysis Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Project planning	0.614	0.393	0.721	0.071	.042
	Project scope planning	0.617	0.291	0.780	0.071	.042
	Resource planning	0.530	0.293	0.721	0.071	.033
	Cost planning and budgeting	0.511	0.494	0.702	0.071	.054
	Quality control	0.412	0.290	0.620	0.071	.033

Using the results in table 4.5 shows that Increasing 1 unit of project planning would increase project performance of the church sponsored projects by 0.721. The statistics also show that the above changes would only be significant for changes. The research revealed that the way projects are planned significantly influences their success, especially when they receive funding from the Catholic Church. These findings align with Larson (2011), who argues that every project and program must be meticulously planned and structured to ensure the fulfillment of stakeholders' rights to survival, protection, growth, and/or involvement. Therefore, involving stakeholders in the planning phase affects both the project's design and the enforcement of their rights to participate. The traditional top-down management strategy is based on the assumption that people are often distracted and possibly less sophisticated, making it challenging to accurately identify and

choose what is beneficial and appropriate for them. Consequently, it is unlikely that they can recognize their own needs for improvement, prioritize them, or identify the most urgent ones.

Furthermore, the research showed that the design and allocation of resources in a project significantly impact its success. It also revealed that while cost planning and budgeting slightly influence the success of projects funded by the Catholic Church, the quality of planning does not significantly affect their performance. These findings are in line with Duncan (2014), who argues that if participants in the planning process lack a clear understanding of the project's objectives, the planning process is likely to be flawed or incorrect. The purpose of defining the project's scope is to outline the time and resources needed to complete the project and satisfy the customer's requirements.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study concluded that project planning positively and significantly affects the performance of Church-funded projects. The study concluded that project scope and resource planning have a major impact on the performance of Church-funded projects. It was found that cost planning and budgeting have a moderate impact on the performance of Church-funded projects, and quality planning has a minor impact on the performance of Church-funded projects.

The research suggests that there's a need for an increased number of individuals skilled in technical areas, particularly in information systems for the purposes of monitoring and assessment. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are advised to ensure comprehensive planning for the monitoring and evaluation of projects, including the allocation of resources and the involvement of stakeholders in both the creation and execution of the monitoring and evaluation framework. It is recommended that competent and seasoned project managers are employed to guarantee the selection of an appropriate project management team for the initiation of project planning processes.

Furthermore, it's crucial to establish a well-structured work program that is rigorously followed, complemented by thorough monitoring and inspection to ensure adherence to the plan and that any modifications are implemented effectively and timely, thereby ensuring the success of construction projects. The concept of managing risks is identified as a fundamental area of expertise in project management by the Project Management Body of Knowledge. It's clear that every project manager aspires to complete a project within the allocated budget, timeframe, quality standards, and customer satisfaction expectations. However, the reality is that achieving these goals is often unattainable due to various obstacles and uncertainties that impede progress. Therefore, it's essential to integrate risk management into the project management process to enhance the likelihood of project completion within the specified parameters.

The research also emphasizes the need to bolster the training and awareness of monitoring and evaluation (M&E) processes and procedures. M&E personnel are encouraged to acquire the necessary M&E skills and knowledge through on-the-job training to maintain their proficiency in this field. Additionally, it's vital for all stakeholders to be actively engaged in the project's monitoring and evaluation activities, as they are the beneficiaries of the project and play a significant role in its sustainability. Fostering cooperation among all parties involved is also recommended.

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